

Publicaciones científicas indexadas relacionadas a biodiversidad de investigadores afiliados a la Universidad del Valle de Guatemala para el período 1971-2025

1. Aguilar, E., López, S. & Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2025). Geographic range extension of *Abronia meledona* to the Pacaya volcano, Escuintla, Guatemala. *Revista Latinoamericana de Herpetología* 8(2): 166–169. <https://doi.org/10.22201/fc.25942158e.2025.2.1271>
2. Álvarez-Yax, R. A., Gómez-Lemus, A. H., Hernández-Fuentes, J. S., Juárez-Bolaños, A. P., Pérez-Quan, K. J., Tijerino-Escobar, D. G., Villatoro-Castañeda, M. & Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2018). Reproducción del falso vampiro lanudo *Chrotopterus auritus* (Chiroptera: Phyllostomidae) en un bosque tropical húmedo de la costa pacífica de Guatemala. *Acta Zoológica Mexicana* 34(1): 104-106. <https://doi.org/10.21829/azm.2018.3411190>
3. Andrade, E., Morales, M. & Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2018). Toxicity of the feathers of Yellow Grosbeak, *Pheucticus chrysopleplus* (Passeriformes: Cardinalidae), a chemically defended neotropical bird. *Revista de Biología Tropical* 66(4): 1530-1535. <https://doi.org/10.15517/rbt.v66i4.32059>
4. Ariano-Sánchez, D. & Campbell, J. (2018). A new species of *Rhadinella* (Serpentes: Dipsadidae) from the dry forest of Motagua Valley, Guatemala. *Zootaxa* 4442 (2): 338-344. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4442.2.10>
5. Ariano-Sánchez, D. & Dix, M. W. (2010). Geographic distribution: Caudata: *Oedipina taylori*. *Herpetological Review* 41(4): 505.
6. Ariano-Sánchez, D. & Gil-Escobedo, J. (2015). Natural History: *Plectrohyla pokomchi* (Rio Sananja spikethumb frog). *Herpetological Review* 46(3): 416.
7. Ariano-Sánchez, D. & Gil-Escobedo, J. (2016). Natural History: *Ctenosaura palearis* (Guatemalan Spiny-tailed Iguana)-Tail trifurcation. *Herpetological Review* 47(3): 463-464.
8. Ariano-Sánchez, D. & Meléndez, L. (2009). Arboreal Alligator lizards in the genus *Abronia*: Emeralds from the cloud forests of Guatemala. *Reptiles and Amphibians: Conservation and Natural History* 16(1): 25-27. <https://doi.org/10.17161/randa.v16i1.15938>
9. Ariano-Sánchez, D. & Salazar, G. (2013). *Heloderma horridum charlesbogerti* (Guatemalan Beaded Lizard)- Wild reproductive ecology. *Herpetological Review* 44 (2): 324.
10. Ariano-Sánchez, D. & Salazar, G. (2015). Spatial ecology of the endangered Guatemalan Beaded Lizard, *Heloderma charlesbogerti*, (Sauria: Helodermatidae) in a tropical dry forest of the Motagua Valley, Guatemala. *Mesoamerican Herpetology* 2: 64-74.
11. Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2008). Envenomation by a wild Guatemalan beaded lizard *Heloderma horridum charlesbogerti*. *Clinical Toxicology* 46 (9): 897-899. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15563650701733031>
12. Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2015). Geographic Distribution: *Tantilla vermiformis* (Hallowell's centipede snake). *Herpetological Review* 46 (2): 221-222.
13. Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2024). First record of partial melanism in the redback coffee snake *Ninia sebae* (Squamata: Dipsadidae). *Revista Latinoamericana de Herpetología* 7(2): 88-89. <https://doi.org/10.22201/fc.25942158e.2024.2.956>

14. Ariano-Sánchez, D., Mortensen, R. M., Wilson, R. P., Bjureke, P., Reinhardt, S. & Rosell, F. (2022). Temperature and Barometric Pressure Affect the Activity Intensity and Movement of an Endangered Thermoconforming Lizard. *Ecosphere* 13(3): e3990. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.3990>
15. Ariano-Sánchez, D., Mortensen, R., Reinhardt, S. & Rosell, F. (2020). Escaping drought: Seasonality effects on home range, movement patterns and habitat selection of the Guatemalan Beaded Lizard. *Global Ecology and Conservation* 23: e01178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2020.e01178>
16. Ariano-Sánchez, D., Muccio, C., Rosell, F. & Reinhardt, S. (2020). Are trends in Olive Ridley sea turtle (*Lepidochelys olivacea*) nesting abundance affected by El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) variability? Sixteen years of monitoring on the Pacific coast of northern Central America. *Global Ecology and Conservation* 24: e01339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2020.e01339>
17. Ariano-Sánchez, D., Nesthus, A., Rosell, F. & Reinhardt, S. (2023). Developed black beaches - too hot to emerge? Factors affecting sand temperatures at nesting grounds of olive ridley sea turtles (*Lepidochelys olivacea*). *Climate Change Ecology* 5: 100074. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecochg.2023.100074>
18. Auliya, M., Altherr, S., Ariano-Sánchez, D., Baard, E., Brown, C., Cantu, J., Gentile, G., Gildenhuis, P., Henningheim, E., Hintzmann, J., Kanari, K., Krvavac, M., Lettink, M., Lippert, J., Luiselli, L., Pasachnik, S. & Zigler, T. (2017). Trade in live reptiles, its impact on wild populations, and the role of the European market. *Biological Conservation* 204: 103-119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2016.05.017>
19. Auliya, M., Nijman, V., Altherr, S., Aguilera, W., Ariano-Sánchez, D., Cantu, J., Colosimo, G., Gentile, G., Gerber, G., Grant, T., Henningheim, E., Hughes, A., Knapp, C., Lieberman, S., Malone, C., Pasachnik, S., Petrossian, G., Sevilla, C., Sosnowski, M. & Weissgold, B. (2025). Trafficking of Galápagos iguanas as an example of a global problem: CITES permits, laundering and the role of transit countries in Europe and Africa. *Biological Conservation* 305: 111104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2025.111104>
20. Baremore, I. E., Polanco-Vásquez, F., Hacohe-Domené, A., Castellanos, D. W. & Graham, R. T. (2019). Short-term movement of a night shark (*Carcharhinus signatus*) in the western Caribbean with notes on the species' distribution and threats in the region. *Environmental Biology of Fishes* 102(3): 519–526. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10641-019-0849-0>
21. Batra, S. & Schuster, J. C. (1977). Nest of *Centris*, *Melissodes*, and *Colletes* in Guatemala (Hymenoptera: Apoidea). *Biotropica* 9(2): 135–138.
22. Becerril-García, E. E., Arauz, R., Arellano-Martínez, M., Bonfil, R., Hoyos-Padilla, E. M., Galván-Magaña, F... & Godard-Codding, C. A. (2022). Research priorities for the conservation of chondrichthyans in Latin America. *Biological Conservation* 269: 109535. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2022.109535>
23. Bezark, L. G., Zack, R. S., Monzón-Sierra, J. & Landolt, P. J. (2019). Known and new records of Disteniidae and Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) from Guatemala. *The Pan-Pacific Entomologist* 95(3/4): 117–125.

24. Bossert, S., Monzón-Sierra, J., Zack, R. S., García, A. C. & Murray, E. A. (2023). Melittological notes from Guatemala (Hymenoptera: Anthophila), I. New country records for *Centris* Fabricius (Apidae) and *Zikanapis* Moure (Colletidae). *Insecta Mundi* 1022: 1–8.
25. Botterell, Z., Ardren, J., Dove, E., McArthur, E., Addison, D., Adegbile, O., Agamboue, P., Agyekumhene, P., Allman, P., Alterman, A., Anderson, A., Arenholz, T. & Ariano-Sánchez, D. et al. (2025). A global assessment of microplastic abundance and characteristics on marine turtle nesting beaches. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 215: 117768. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2025.117768>
26. Cadena-Castañeda, O. J. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (2014). A new species of the genus *Onychopygia* Beier (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae: Pseudophyllinae) from Guatemala. *Insecta Mundi* 0329: 1–8.
27. Cadena-Castañeda, O. J. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (2014). Studies in Guatemalan Caelifera: New grasshoppers and monkey grasshoppers (Orthoptera: Caelifera: Acridoidea & Eumastacoidea) and an updated checklist. *Zootaxa* 3857 (3): 379–411. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.3857.3.3>
28. Cadena-Castañeda, O. J. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (2017). Studies in Guatemalan Ensifera: New *Glaphyrosoma* species (Orthoptera: Anostomatidae) and additional data for other described species. *Zootaxa* 4242(3): 548–564. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4242.3.7>
29. Cadena-Castañeda, O. J., Monzón-Sierra, J. & Cortéz-Torres, C. (2016). Studies in Guatemalan Ensifera: *Mayacephalus* (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae) a new cone-headed katydid genus. *Zootaxa* 4084 (2): 293–300. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4084.2.9>
30. Cano, E. B. & Schuster, J. C. (1995). A new species of *Petrejoides* from Guatemala and comments on *Petrejoides michoacanae* (Coleoptera: Passalidae). *The Florida Entomologist* 78(2): 246–250.
31. Cano, E. B. & Schuster, J. C. (2008). Beetles as indicators for forest conservation in Central America. *Encyclopedia of Life Support Systems (EOLSS)*, UNESCO-EOLSS. <http://www.eolss.net/ebooks/Sample%20Chapters/C20/E6-142-TPE-04.pdf>
32. Cano, E. B. & Schuster, J. C. (2012). A new species of *Oileus* Kaup (Coleoptera, Passalidae) from Guatemala, with a key to the species of the genus. *ZooKeys* 194: 81–87. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.194.2963>
33. Cano, E. B., Schuster, J. C. & Morrone, J. J. (2018). Phylogenetics of *Ogyges* Kaup and the biogeography of Nuclear Central America (Coleoptera, Passalidae). *ZooKeys* 737: 81–111. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.737.20741>
34. Cerutti-Pereyra, F., Drenkard, E. J., Espinoza, M., Finucci, B., Galván-Magaña, F., Hacothen-Domené, A., Hearn, A., Hoyos-Padilla, M. E., Ketchum, J. T., Mejía-Falla, P. A., Moya-Serrano, A. V., Navia, A. F., Pazmiño, D. A., Ramírez-Macías, D., Rummer, J. L., Salinas-de-León, P., Sosa-Nishizaki, O., Stock, C. & Chin, A. (2024). Vulnerability of Eastern Tropical Pacific chondrichthyan fish to climate change. *Global Change Biology* 30(7): e17373. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.17373>
35. Dahinten-Bailey, H., Serrano, M., Alonso-Ascencio, M., Cruz-Font, J., Rosito-Prado, I., Ruiz-Villanueva, K., Vázquez-Almazán, C. & Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2021). A new species of *Bolitoglossa* (Caudata: Plethodontidae) of the *Bolitoglossa franklini* group from an isolated cloud forest in northern Guatemala. *Zootaxa* 4966: 202–214. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4966.2.7>
36. Dix, M. A. & Dix, M. W. (2003). Polinización de orquídeas en Guatemala: los polinizadores, el estado natural de sus poblaciones y las implicaciones para las especies polinizadas. *Lankesteriana* 3(7): 97.

37. Dix, M. W. & Dix, M. A. (2000). *Orchids of Guatemala: a revised annotated checklist*. Monographs in systematic botany. Vol. 78. Missouri Botanical Garden Press.
38. Dix, M. W. & Dix, M. A. (2003). *Rhynchostele bictoniensis*: cambios en abundancia y éxito de polinización entre 1992 y 2002. *Lankesteriana* 3(7): 98.
39. Dix, M. W. & Dix, M. A. (2007). Integrated approaches to orchid conservation in Guatemala: past, present and future, opportunities and challenges. *Lankesteriana* 7(1–2): 266–268.
40. Dyson, C., Pfennig, A., Ariano-Sánchez, D., Lachance, J., Mendelson III, J. & Goodisman, M. (2022). Genome of the endangered Guatemalan Beaded Lizard, *Heloderma charlesbogerti*, reveals evolutionary relationships of squamates and declines in effective population sizes. *G3 Genes|Genomes|Genetics* 12: jkac276. <https://doi.org/10.1093/g3journal/jkac276>
41. Eisermann, K., Lewis, G. P., Forest, F., Gagnon, E., Csiba, L., Aju, J. & Williamson, J. (2025). *Erythrostemon guatemalensis* (Leguminosae: Caesalpinioideae: Caesalpinieae), a new Endangered tree species from the Pacific Slope highlands of Guatemala. *Kew Bulletin* 80: 663–678. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12225-025-10300-0>
42. Escobar-Anleu, B., Fuentes-Montejo, C. & Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2017). Registros de mamíferos (Mammalia: Didelphimorphia, Artiodactyla, Carnivora, Cingulata, Lagomorpha, Pilosa y Rodentia) en Reservas Naturales Privadas. *Acta Zoológica Mexicana* 33(2): 388-392. <https://doi.org/10.21829/azm.2017.3321077>
43. Frank, J. H., Giardina, D, Andrus, T. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (2007). Searching in Guatemala for more parasitoids to use against *Metamasius callizona* in Florida. *Journal of the Bromeliad Society* 57(6): 253–258.
44. García-Cordón, A. C., León-Coloma, A. R., Zack, R. S. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (2025). First records of the Yucatán cracker butterfly, *Hamadryas julitta* (Fruhstorfer, 1914) (Lepidoptera: Nymphalidae: Biblidinae), from the Mayan Biosphere Reserve, Guatemala. *The Pan-Pacific Entomologist* 101(4): 330–335. <https://doi.org/10.3956/2025-101.4.330>
45. García-Cordón, A. C., Monzón-Sierra, J., Zack, R. S. & Bossert, S. (2025). Melittological notes from Guatemala (Hymenoptera: Anthophila), 2. New country records for Apidae (Anthophorini and Centridini) and Halictidae (Augochlorini). *Insecta Mundi* 1127: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.64338/im.1127.by5kg>
46. García-Díaz, J., Nuñez-Robles, D. & Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2024). First record of albinism in tadpoles of *Ptychohyla euthysanota* (Anura: Hylidae). *Revista Latinoamericana de Herpetología* 7(1): e837. <https://doi.org/10.22201/fc.25942158e.2024.1.837>
47. García-Rodríguez, E., Gonzalez-Pestana, A., Charles, R., Palacios, M. D., Notarbartolo di Sciara, G., Alfaro-Shigueto, J., Avalos-Castillo, C. G., Chávez, E. J., Espinoza, M., Hacoheh-Domené, A., Hearn, A. R., Galván-Magaña, F., Ketchum, J. T., Lara-Lizardi, F., Morales-Saldaña, J. M., Morales Serrano, N., Mejía-Falla, P. A., Navia, A. F., Peñaherrera-Palma, C. R., Polanco-Vásquez, F., Rodríguez-Arriatti, Y., Saldaña-Ruiz, L. E., Sosa-Nishizaki, O., Velez-Zuazo, X. & Jabado, R. W. (2025). Mapping Important Shark and Ray Areas (ISRAs) in the Central and South American Pacific: Existing knowledge and data needs. *PLOS ONE* 20(5): e0322445. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0322445>

48. Gil-Escobedo, J., Salazar-Asencio, G., Yanes-Morán, F., Chinchilla Putzeys, C., García-Anleu, R., Luis-Valenzuela, S., García, W., Echeverría-Méndez, A. & Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2024). Observations on the nesting behavior of the Yucatan Spiny-tailed Iguana *Cachryx defensor* (Squamata: Iguanidae) in its natural habitat. *Revista Latinoamericana de Herpetología* 7(3): 1-3.
<https://doi.org/10.22201/fc.25942158e.2024.3.969>
49. Gluszek, S., Ariano-Sánchez, D., Cremona, P., Goynechea, A., Luque, D., McLoughlin, L., Morales, A., Reuter, A., Rodríguez, J., Radachowsky, J. & Knight, A. (2021). Emerging trends of the illegal wildlife trade in Mesoamerica. *Oryx* 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0030605319001133>
50. Gómez-Cruz, A., Santos-Hernández, N., Cruz, J., Ariano-Sánchez, D., Ruiz-Castillejos, C., Espinoza-Medinilla, E. & De Fuentes-Vicente, J. (2021). Effect of climate change on the potential distribution of *Heloderma alvarezii* (Squamata, Helodermatidae). *ZooKeys* 1070: 1–12.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.1070.69186>
51. González, F. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (2022). An updated synopsis of *Aristolochia* (Aristolochiaceae) in Guatemala. *Brittonia* 74: 239-264. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12228-022-09704-0>
52. Gorneau, J. A., Jones, D. L., Monzón-Sierra, J. & Jason, J. J. (2023). Three new species of the genus *Argyresthia* Hübner, [1825] from Guatemala, with notes on host plant evolution and Nearctic taxa (Lepidoptera: Argyresthiidae). *SHILAP* 51(201): 159–181. <https://doi.org/10.57065/shilap.444>
53. Hacoheñ-Domené, A., Polanco-Vásquez, F., Estupiñan-Montaño, C. & Graham, R. T. (2020). Description and characterization of the artisanal elasmobranch fishery on Guatemala's Caribbean coast. *PLoS ONE* 15(1): e0227797. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0227797>
54. Herbin, D. & Monzón, J. (2020). Biodiversity in Guatemala: description of five new species of Mimallonidae (Lepidoptera: Mimallonoidea). *Antenor* 7(1): 69–79.
55. Herbin, D. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (2015). Description of four new species of Mimallonidae and four new species of Apatelodidae from the El Mirador Basin in northern Guatemala. *Antenor* 2(2): 176–197.
56. Hernández-Baz, F., Bailey, A. C. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (2008). Notes on some Ctenuchinae dry season (Lepidoptera: Arctiidae) from a cloud forest and pine-oak forest in Guatemala, Middle America. *Dugesiana* 15(2): 87–89.
57. Jiménez-Ferbans, L., Reyes-Castillo, P. & Schuster, J. C. (2015). Passalidae (Coleoptera: Scarabaeoidea) of the Greater and Lesser Antilles. *Zootaxa* 3956 (4): 491–512.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.3956.4.3>
58. Jiménez-Ferbans, L., Reyes-Castillo, P. & Schuster, J. C. (2018). Passalidae (Coleoptera: Scarabaeoidea) of the Biogeographical Province of Chocó and the West Andean Region of Colombia, with the Description of Two New Species. *Neotropical Entomology* 47: 642-667.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13744-017-0584-1>
59. Jiménez-Ferbans, L., Reyes-Castillo, P., Schuster, J. C. & Salazar, K. (2013). A checklist and key for the identification of bess beetles (Coleoptera: Passalidae) of Argentina. *Zootaxa* 3701 (2): 192–206.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.3701.2.4>
60. Jiménez-Ferbans, L., Reyes-Castillo, P., Schuster, J. C. & Upegui-Velez, C. (2016). *Passalus coarctatus* Percheron, 1835 (Coleoptera: Passalidae): redescription and new distributional records. *Acta Zoológica Mexicana* 32(2): 168-173. <https://doi.org/10.21829/azm.2016.322944>

61. Jiménez-Ferbans, L., Reyes-Castillo, P., Schuster, J. C. & Upegui-Vélez, C. (2017). The passalid beetles (Coleoptera: Passalidae) from Costa Rica, with the description of two new species of *Passalus*. *Revista Mexicana de Biodiversidad* 88: 608–615. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rmb.2017.07.016>
62. Laguerre, M. Monzón-Sierra, J. & De Souza-Moraes, S. (2014). Description of two new species of Pericopini from Guatemala and critical review of some recent nomenclature changes in the genus *Dysschema* Hübner (Lepidoptera: Erebiidae: Arctiinae: Pericopini). *Journal of Insect Biodiversity* 2(4): 1–19.
63. Landolt, P. J., Monzón-Sierra, J., Unruh, TH. R. & Zak, R. (2010). A new species of *Vespula*, and first record of *Vespa crabro* L. (Hymenoptera: Vespidae) from Guatemala, Central America. *Zootaxa* 2629: 61-68. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.2629.1.4>
64. Landolt, P. J., Reed, H. C. Landolt, K. N., Monzón-Sierra, J. & Zack, R. (2009). The Southern Yellowjacket, *Vespula squamosa* (Drury) (Hymenoptera: Vespidae) In Guatemala, Central America. *Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Washington* 111(2): 426–432.
65. Lemaire, C., Wolfe, K. L. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (2001). A new *Hylesia* from Guatemala (Lepidoptera: Saturniidae, Hemileucinae). *Nachrichten des entomologischen Vereins Apollo* NF 22(3): 171–173.
66. Lindken, T., Anderson, C., Ariano-Sánchez, D., Barki, G., Biggs, C., Bowles, P., Chaitanya, R., Cronin, D., Jahning, S., Jeschke, J., Kennerley, R., Lacher, T., Luedtke, J., Liu, C., Long, B., Mallon, D., Martin, G., Meri, S., Pasachnik, S., Reynoso, V., Stanford, C., Stephenson, P., Tolley, K., Torres-Carvajal, O., Waldien, D., Woinarski, J. & Evans, T. (2024). What factors influence the rediscovery of lost tetrapod species? *Global Change Biology* 30: 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.17107>
67. Lipinska, M., López-Selva, M. M. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (2024). Biodiversity research in Central America. *Neotropical Biology and Conservation* 19(2).
68. Magalhães, C. & Wehrtmann, I. S. (2025). Taxonomic revision and distribution of the freshwater crabs of the family Pseudothelphusidae (Decapoda, Brachyura) from Guatemala, with the descriptions of two new species and keys to the species of all genera. *Zoosystema* 47(26): 581-615. <https://doi.org/10.5252/zoosystema2025v47a26>
69. Magalhães, C., Wehrtmann, I. S. & Mantelatto, F. L. (2025). Revalidation of *Ptychophallus campylus* Pretzmann, 1968, a freshwater crab species from Costa Rica (Decapoda: Brachyura: Pseudothelphusidae). *Revista de Biología Tropical* 73(S2): e64534.
70. MacVean, C. & Schuster, J. C. (1981). Altitudinal distribution of passalid beetles (Coleoptera, Passalidae) and Pleistocene dispersal on the volcanic chain of northern Central America. *Biotropica* 13(1): 29-38.
71. MacVean, C. M., Schuster, J. C. & Cano, E. B. (2001). Adaptive radiation in the tropics. Entomology at the Universidad del Valle de Guatemala. *American Entomologist* 47(3): 138-144.
72. Marshall, R. S., Monzón-Sierra, J. & Know-Jones, J. JR. (1991). The big spear-nosed bat, *Phyllostomus hastatus* (Chiroptera: Phyllostomidae), in Guatemala. *The Texas Journal of Science* 43(1): 106–107.
73. Mielke, C. G. C., Grehan, J. R. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (2020). Taxonomic revision of *Schausiana* Viette with two new species from Guatemala and notes on biogeography and correlated tectonics (Lepidoptera: Hepialidae). *Zootaxa* 4860 (1): 067–091. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4860.1.3>.

74. Mielke, C. G. C., Grehan, J. R. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (2022). *Weymerella* gen. n. with description of two new species from Mexico and Guatemala (Lepidoptera: Hepialidae). *Nachrichten des entomologischen Vereins Apollo* N.F. 43(2): 92–101.
75. M6, E. A., Garc3a-Mart3nez, R. & Monz3n-Sierra, J. (2021). *Tillandsia atitlanensis* (Bromeliaceae: Tillandsioideae), una nueva especie guatemalteca con flores blancas. *Lacandonia* 15(1): 23–30.
76. Monz3n-Sierra, J. & Ballmer, G. R. (2022). Natural history of the Guatemalan copper *Iophanus pyrrhias* (Godman and Salvin, 1887) (Lepidoptera: Lycaenidae) in Guatemala. *The Taxonomic Report* 10(1): 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16419766>.
77. Monz3n-Sierra, J. & Cano, E. B. (1999). *Plusiotis ericsmithii* (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae): a new metallic species from eastern Guatemala. *Insecta Mundi* 13(3–4): 213–215.
78. Monz3n-Sierra, J. & Garc3a, L. J. (2011). Two new species of *Chrysina* Kirby (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Rutelinae) from Mexico. *Insecta Mundi* 0195: 1–8.
79. Monz3n-Sierra, J. & Hawks, D. C. (2020). A new cryptic species of metallic *Chrysina* Kirby (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Rutelinae) from western Honduras. *Insecta Mundi* 0802: 1–5.
80. Monz3n-Sierra, J. & Schuster, J. C. (2013). *Mayab Yik'elil Kan: Los insectos tropicales del antiguo reino kan de mesoam3rica*. 167 pp.
81. Monz3n-Sierra, J. & Wolfe, K. L. (1999). Lista preliminar de las especies de la familia del "gusano de pino" en Guatemala (Lepidoptera: Saturniidae). *Revista Nicaraguense de Entomolog3a* 48: 29–35.
82. Monz3n-Sierra, J. & Zack, R. S. (2025). *Dynastes septentrionalis* Lachaume, 1985 (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Dynastinae) in Guatemala: Male morphological variation, distribution, and ecological notes. *The Pan-Pacific Entomologist* 101(4): 353–370. <https://doi.org/10.3956/2025-101.4.353>.
83. Monz3n-Sierra, J. (1995). Guatemalan *Plusiotis* and *Chrysina* (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Rutelinae): new records. *Insecta Mundi* 9(3–4): 347–349.
84. Monz3n-Sierra, J. (2010). Three new species of *Chrysina* Kirby (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae; Rutelinae) from Guatemala and Mexico. *Insecta Mundi* 0143: 1–12.
85. Monz3n-Sierra, J. (2012). A new species of *Chrysina* Kirby (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Rutelinae) from Oaxaca, Mexico. *Insecta Mundi* 0215: 1–4.
86. Monz3n-Sierra, J. (2017). Four new species of *Chrysina* Kirby (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Rutelinae) from Guatemala and Honduras. *Insecta Mundi* 0543: 1–12.
87. Monz3n-Sierra, J., Blackaller-Bages, J. F. & Hawks, D. C. (2020). Description of a new species of *Chrysina* Kirby (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Rutelinae) from the Sierra Azul, Oaxaca, Mexico, a new synonymy, and notes on *Chrysina* species found in the Sierra Azul. *Insecta Mundi* 0803: 1–7.
88. Monz3n-Sierra, J., Cano, E. B & Bailey, A. C. (1999). Notes on Guatemalan *Plusiotis* (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae; Rutelinae). *Insecta Mundi* 13(3–4): 183–188.
89. Morales, A., Ariano-S3nchez, D. & Mor3n, D. (2015). Geographic Distribution: *Gerrhonotus liocephalus* (Wiegmann's alligator lizard). *Herpetological Review* 46 (2): 217.
90. Mouton, T. L., Gonzalez-Pestana, A., Rohner, C. A., Charles, R., Garc3a-Rodr3guez, E., Kyne, P. M., Batlle-Morera, A., di Sciara, G. N., Armstrong, A. O., Acuña, E.... & Jabado, R. W. (2025). Shortfalls in the protection of Important Shark and Ray Areas undermine shark conservation efforts in the Central

- and South American Pacific. *Marine Policy* 171: 106448.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2024.106448>
91. Naumann, S. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (2021). The species-complex of *Copaxa sophronia* Schaus, 1921, with description of two new species (Lepidoptera: Saturniidae, Saturniinae). *Nachrichten des entomologischen Vereins Apollo* 42(1/2): 36–45.
 92. Norrbom, A. L., Sutton, B. D., Steck, G. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (2010). New genera, species and host plant records of Nearctic and Neotropical Tephritidae (Diptera). *Zootaxa* 2398: 1–65.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.2398.1.1>.
 93. Ordoñez, N., MacCarthy, T. J., Monzón-Sierra, J., Matson, J. O. & Eckerlin, R. (1999). Ampliación del área de distribución de *Bassaricyon gabbii* J. A. Allen, 1876 (Carnivora: Procyonidae) en el norte de América Central. *The Southwestern Naturalist* 53(4): 507–538.
 94. Orellana, K. S., López, Z. M., Quezada, M. L., Yoshimoto, J., Prado, L. M., Ambrocio, A. L., Franz & Gilbert, E. (2025). Five Years of the Guatemala Biodiversity Portal: Increasing Capacities for the Mobilization of Natural History Collections Using Symbiota. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards* 9: e178671. <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.9.178671>.
 95. Padilla, E. & Schuster, J. C. (1994). *Klinckowstroemia multisetilosa* Rosario & Hunter (Acarina: Trigynaspida: Klinckowstroemidae) associated with three species of *Proculus* Kuwert (Coleoptera: Passalidae). *Acta Zoológica Mexicana* 61: 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.21829/azm.1994.61611663>.
 96. Pennington, P. M. & Yoshimoto, J. (2023). First Record of a Secondary Chagas Disease Vector *Triatoma nitida* in High-Altitude Region. *The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* 113(6): 1211–1212. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.25-0272>.
 97. Pineda-Schwarz, D., Alonso-Asencio, M., Arrivillaga-Cano, E., Cruz-Font, J., Dahinten-Bailey, H., Rosito-Prado, I. & Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2018). Geographic Distribution: *Nyctanolis pernix*. *Herpetological Review* 49 (3): 499-500.
 98. Reyes, G., Monzón-Sierra, J. & Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2022). Rediscovery after 48 years and geographic range extension of *Abronia anzueto* (Campbell & Frost, 1993) (Squamata: Anguillidae) from Agua Volcano, Guatemala. *Revista Latinoamericana de Herpetología* 5(4): 108–111.
<https://doi.org/10.22201/fc.25942158e.2022.4.554>.
 99. Reyes-Castillo, P. & Schuster, J. C. (1983). Notes on some Mesoamerican Passalidae (Coleoptera): *Petrejoides* and *Pseudacanthus*. *The Coleopterists Bulletin* 37(1): 49-53.
 100. Ruiz-Villanueva, K., Piedrasanta-López, J. & Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2018). Leucism in *Bolitoglossa engelhardti* (Caudata: Plethodontidae), with notes on elevational distribution. *Mesoamerican Herpetology* 5(1): 193-195.
 101. Schuster, J. C. & Bonis, S. (2008). Biodiversidad de Guatemala en relación a su historia geológica y Biogeografía. pp. 21-53. En: *Biodiversidad de Guatemala*. Azurdia, C. (ed.). CONAP, Guatemala.
 102. Schuster, J. C. & Cano, E. B. (2006). What can Scarabaeoidea contribute to the knowledge of the biogeography of Guatemala? *Coleopterists Society Monograph* 5, *Coleopterists Bulletin Supplement* 60: 57-70.

103. Schuster, J. C. & Cano, E. B. (2008). Taxonomy of Passalidae of the New World. <http://www.museum.unl.edu/research/entomology/Guide/Scarabaeoidea/Passalidae/Passalidae-Taxonomy.pdf>.
104. Schuster, J. C. & Clark, S. (1989). Taxonomía y sistemática en el manejo de plagas. En: *Manejo integrado de plagas insectiles en la agricultura*. Andrews, K. & Quezada, J. R. (eds.). Zamorano, Honduras.
105. Schuster, J. C. & Reyes-Castillo, P. (1981). New world genera of Passalidae (Coleoptera): a revision of larvae. *Anales de la Escuela Nacional de Ciencias Biológicas de México* 25: 79-116.
106. Schuster, J. C. & Reyes-Castillo, P. (1990). Coleoptera, Passalidae: *Ogyges* Kaup, revisión de un género mesoamericano de montaña. *Acta Zoológica Mexicana* 40: 1-49. <https://doi.org/10.21829/azm.1990.37401645>.
107. Schuster, J. C. & Reyes-Castillo, P. (1990). Passalidae: New larval descriptions from Taiwan, Philippine Islands, Brunei and Ivory Coast. *The Florida Entomologist* 73(2): 267-273.
108. Schuster, J. C. & Schuster, L. B. (1971). Un esbozo de señales auditivas y comportamiento de Passalidae (Coleoptera) del Nuevo Mundo. *Revista Peruana de Entomología* 14(2): 249-252.
109. Schuster, J. C. & Schuster, L. B. (1985). Social behavior in passalid beetles (Coleoptera: Passalidae): Cooperative brood care. *The Florida Entomologist* 68(2): 266-272.
110. Schuster, J. C. & Schuster, L. B. (1997). The evolution of social behavior in Passalidae (Coleoptera). pp. 260-269. En: *The evolution of social behavior in insects and arachnids*. Choe, J. C. & Crespi, J. (eds.). Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, Reino Unido.
111. Schuster, J. C. & Steele, G. (2015). Phenology of *Zagryphus zulaya* Gauld (Ichneumonidae: Tryphoninae) in a Montane Forest in Guatemala and a New Country Record for *Z. vegai* Gauld. *Insecta Mundi* 0447: 1-7.
112. Schuster, J. C. (1974). Saltatorial Orthoptera as common visitors to tropical flowers. *Biotropica* 6(2): 138-140.
113. Schuster, J. C. (1975). A comparative study of copulation in Passalidae (Coleoptera): New positions for beetles. *The Coleopterists Bulletin* 29(2): 75-81.
114. Schuster, J. C. (1978). Biogeographical and ecological limits of New World Passalidae (Coleoptera). *The Coleopterists Bulletin* 32(1): 21-28.
115. Schuster, J. C. (1981). Stingless bees attending honeydewproducing treehoppers in Guatemala. *The Florida Entomologist* 64(1): 192.
116. Schuster, J. C. (1983). Acoustical signals of passalid beetles: complex repertoires. *The Florida Entomologist* 66(4): 486-496.
117. Schuster, J. C. (1983). The Passalidae of the Galapagos Islands. *The Coleopterists Bulletin* 37(4): 299-301.
118. Schuster, J. C. (1983). The Passalidae of the United States. *The Coleopterists Bulletin* 37(4): 302-305.
119. Schuster, J. C. (1984). Passalid beetle (Coleoptera: Passalidae) inhabitants of leafcutter ant (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) detritus. *The Florida Entomologist* 67(1): 175-176.

120. Schuster, J. C. (1985). La enseñanza de entomología y manejo de plagas en la Universidad del Valle de Guatemala. *Ceiba* 26(1): 16-19.
121. Schuster, J. C. (1988). *Petrejoides reyesi* sp. nov. (Coleoptera: Passalidae) from Honduras. *The Coleopterists Bulletin* 42(4): 305-309.
122. Schuster, J. C. (1989). Claves para identificar insectos inmaduros holometabolos. *Manejo Integrado de Plagas (Costa Rica)* 11: 61-74.
123. Schuster, J. C. (1990). *Petrejoides salvadorae* sp. nov. (Coleoptera: Passalidae) from El Salvador. *The Florida Entomologist* 72(4): 693-696.
124. Schuster, J. C. (1991). Arthropod collecting in Guatemala. *Insect Collection News* 6: 14-15.
125. Schuster, J. C. (1991). *Heliscus* and *Verres* (Coleoptera: Passalidae): New species records from Guatemala and Panama. *The Florida Entomologist* 74(3): 475-476.
126. Schuster, J. C. (1991). *Petrejoides* (Col: Passalidae): Four new species from Mesoamerica and Mexico with a key to the genus. *The Florida Entomologist* 74(3): 422-432.
127. Schuster, J. C. (1992). Arthropod collecting and forest conservation in Guatemala. *Insect Collection News* 8: 15-16.
128. Schuster, J. C. (1992). Biotic areas and the distribution of passalid beetles (Coleoptera) in northern Central America: post-Pleistocene montane refuges. En: *Biogeography of Mesoamerica*. New Orleans, Tulane University. pp. 285-292.
129. Schuster, J. C. (1992). Insect collections and biodiversity in Guatemala. *Association of Systematics Collections Newsletter* 20(1): 90-91.
130. Schuster, J. C. (1992). Passalidae: State of larval taxonomy with description of New World species. *The Florida Entomologist* 75(3): 357-369.
131. Schuster, J. C. (1993). Passalidae: Clave para géneros de Colombia. *Boletín del Museo de Entomología de la Universidad del Valle, Colombia* 1(2): 55-61.
132. Schuster, J. C. (1993). *Xylopassaloides* (Coleoptera: Passalidae) in Mesoamerica: Relations, distribution and new species. *The Florida Entomologist* 76(1): 114-119.
133. Schuster, J. C. (1994). *Odontotaenius floridanus* new species (Coleoptera: Passalidae): A second U.S. passalid beetle. *The Florida Entomologist* 77(4): 474-479.
134. Schuster, J. C. (1997). Seasonal diversity of fireflies (Coleoptera:Lampyridae) in a montane area of Guatemala. En: *Tropical systematics in tropical ecosystems*. Ulrich, H. (ed.). Bonn, Alemania.
135. Schuster, J. C. (1998). Chemical prospecting: An evolutionary-biogeographical approach – mesoamerican cloud forests as an example. *Pure and Applied Chemistry* 70(11): 2112.
136. Schuster, J. C. (2001). Passalidae Leach 1815. Bess beetle family.
<http://www.museum.unl.edu/research/entomology/Guide/PassalidaeO.htm>.
137. Schuster, J. C. (2002). Passalidae Leach 1815. Bess beetle family. En: *American Beetles. Polyphaga: Scarabaeoidea through Curculionioidea*. Arnett, R. H., Thomas, M. C., Skelley, P. E. & Frank, J. H. (eds.). CRC Press, Boca Ratón, Florida.
138. Schuster, J. C. (2008). *Bess beetles (Coleoptera: Passalidae)*. pp. 272-274. En: *Encyclopedia of Entomology*. Capinera, J. (ed.). Springer, Berlin.

139. Schuster, J. C., Cano, E. B. & Boucher, S. (2005). *Ogyges* and *Veturius* (Coleoptera: Passalidae) in Central America: Synonymies, range extensions and new species. *Acta Zoológica Mexicana* 21(2): 115-132. <https://doi.org/10.21829/azm.2005.2121990>.
140. Schuster, J. C., Cano, E. B. & Cardona, C. (2000). Un método sencillo para priorizar la conservación de los bosques nubosos de Guatemala, usando Passalidae (Coleoptera) como organismos indicadores. *Acta Zoológica Mexicana* 80: 197-209. <https://doi.org/10.21829/azm.2000.80801900>.
141. Schuster, J. C., Cano, E. B. & Reyes-Castillo, P. (2003). *Proculus*, giant Latin-American Passalids: revision, phylogeny and biogeography. *Acta Zoológica Mexicana* 90: 281-306. <https://doi.org/10.21829/azm.2003.902555>.
142. Schuster, L. B. & Schuster, J. C. (1971). Interacciones diurnas entre insectos y las flores de *Tripogandra cumanaensis* (Commelinaceae). *Revista Peruana de Entomología* 14(2): 253-258.
143. Serrano, M. J., Grajeda-Estrada, R., Villalobos, A., Álvarez-Ruano, M. R. & Vázquez-García, J. A. (2020). *Magnolia poqomchi*, a new species of subsection *Magnolia* (Magnoliaceae) from San Cristóbal Verapaz, Alta Verapaz, Guatemala. *Phytotaxa* 454(4): 231–243. <https://doi.org/10.11646/phytotaxa.454.4.1>.
144. Serrano, M., Cruz, J., Villatoro-Castañeda, M. & Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2018). Tremulation display in male agonistic behavior of the black-eyed leaf frog (*Agalychnis moreletii*: Hylidae). *Animal Behavior and Cognition* 5(2): 222-228. <https://doi.org/10.26451/abc.05.02.04.2018>.
145. Stonis, J. R., Diskus, A., Remeikis, A. & Schuster, J. (2013). First discovery of *Quercus* feeding Nepticulidae (Lepidoptera) in Central America. *Zootaxa* 3737(1): 001-023. <http://dx.doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.3737.1.1>.
146. Stonis, J. R., Diskus, A., Remeikis, A., Noreika, R. & Schuster, J. (2013). Four new leaf-mining *Acalyptris* species from Guatemala and Belize, with new data on bionomics of *Stigmella pruinosa* (Lepidoptera: Nepticulidae). *Zootaxa* 3737(2): 101–117. <http://dx.doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.3737.2.1>.
147. Thiaucourt, P. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (2013). *Symmerista brucestutoni* nouvelle espèce du Guatemala (Lepidoptera, Notodontidae). *Bulletin de la Société Entomologique de Mulhouse* 69(1): 13–14.
148. Torres, M., Urbina, A., Vásquez-Almazán, C., Pierson, T. & Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2013). Geographic Distribution: *Abronia lythrochila* (red-lipped arboreal alligator lizard). *Herpetological Review* 44(4): 624.
149. Urbina, H., Schuster, J. & Blackwell, M. (2013). The gut of Guatemalan passalid beetles: a habitat colonized by cellobiose- and xylose-fermenting yeasts. *Fungal Ecology* 6: 339-355. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.funeco.2013.06.005>.
150. Vásquez-Contreras, A. & Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2016). Endozoochory by the Guatemalan Black Iguana, *Ctenosaura palearis* (Iguanidae), as a germination trigger for the Organ Pipe Cactus *Stenocereus pruinosus* (Cactaceae). *Mesoamerican Herpetology* 3(3): 662–668.
151. Villatoro-Castañeda, M. & Ariano-Sánchez, D. (2017). Rediscovery of the Guatemalan Yellow-lipped Snake *Chapinophis xanthocheilus* (Serpentes: Dipsadidae) with comments on its distribution and ecology. *Herpetological Review* 48(1): 25-28.

152. Warner, W. B. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (1993). A new *Plusiotis* from Guatemala and Belize (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae). *Insecta Mundi* 7(1): 211–214.
153. Whitehead, D. A., Murillo-Cisneros, D., Elorriaga-Verplancken, F. R., Hacoheh-Domené, A., De La Parra, R., Gonzalez-Armas, R. & Galvan-Magaña, F. (2020). Stable isotope assessment of whale sharks across two ocean basins: Gulf of California and the Mexican Caribbean. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 527: 151359. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2020.151359>
154. Yang, C., Freeman, M. C., Wehrtmann, I. S., Rugenski, A. T. & Wenger, S. J. (2025). Patterns of Freshwater Crab (Decapoda: Brachyura: Pseudothelphusidae) Abundances in Costa Rican Headwater Streams. *Biotropica* 57: e70064. <https://doi.org/10.1111/btp.70064>
155. Yoshimoto, J. & Salinas-Gutiérrez, J. L. (2015). First record of *Atlides gaumeri* and Noes on *Chalybs hassan* in Guatemala. *Southwestern Entomologist* 40(3): 497–501.
156. Yoshimoto, J., Salinas-Gutiérrez, J. L., Barrios, M. & Warren, A. D. (2022). An updated list of butterflies (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea) of two Guatemalan seasonally dry forests. *ZooKeys* 1118(1): 21–38. <https://zookeys.pensoft.net/article/85810/>.
157. Yoshimoto, J., Barrios, M., Salinas-Gutiérrez, J. L. & Warren, A. D. (2021). Fauna y fenología de mariposas diurnas (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea) de un bosque secundario en el área urbana de Guatemala. *Revista Mexicana de Biodiversidad* 92: e923469. <https://doi.org/10.22201/ib.20078706e.2021.92.3469>.
158. Yoshimoto, J., Powell, G. & Cline, A. R. (2018). Flower-Inhabiting Sap Beetles (Coleoptera: Nitidulidae: Carpophilinae) in Guatemala. *The Coleopterists Bulletin* <https://doi.org/10.1649/0010-065X-72.4.762>.
159. Yoshimoto, J., Salinas-Gutiérrez, J. L. & Barrios, M. (2018). Annotated list of butterflies (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea) of a Guatemalan dry forest, with two first record for Guatemala. *Tropical Lepidoptera Research* 28(1): 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1248159>.
160. Yoshimoto, J., Salinas-Gutiérrez, J. L. & Barrios, M. (2019). Butterfly Fauna and Phenology in a Dry Forest of the Motagua Valley, Guatemala. *Journal of the Lepidopterist's Society* 73(3): 191–202. <https://doi.org/10.18473/lepi.73i3.a8>.
161. Zack, R. S., Henry, T. J. & Monzón-Sierra, J. (2022). Annotated checklist of the stilt bugs (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Berytidae) of Guatemala, with new country records. *The Pan-Pacific Entomologist* 97(4): 195–209.
162. Zack, R. S., Monzón-Sierra, J. & Sites, W. R. (2021). New country record for *Lepidocnemeplatia laticollis* (Champion, 1885) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) from Guatemala. *The Pan-Pacific Entomologist* 97(2): 81–84.
163. Zack, R. S., Monzón-Sierra, J., Green, N. M. D. & Bush, T. (2025). First records of *Phorticus collaris* Stal, 1873 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Nabidae) in Costa Rica, Guatemala, Nicaragua, and Panama with notes on its distribution range. *The Pan-Pacific Entomologist* 101(4): 371–375.
164. Zack, R. S., Monzón-Sierra, J., Huether, J. P., Huether, M. K. & Landolt, P. J. (2023). New country records of blister beetles (Coleoptera: Meloidae) from Guatemala with distributional notes on other meloid species and a record of human blistering cause by *Epicauta (Macrobasis) forticornis* Haag-Rutenberg, 1880. *The Pan-Pacific Entomologist* 99(3): 169–182.

165. Zumbado-Ulate, H., Neam, K., García-Rodríguez, A., Ochoa-Ochoa, L., Chaves, G., Kolby, J., Granados-Martínez, S., Hertz, A., Bolaños, F., Ariano-Sánchez, D., Puschendorf, R. & Searle, C. (2022). Ecological correlates of extinction risk and persistence of direct-developing stream-dwelling frogs in Mesoamerica. *Global Ecology and Conservation* 38: e02197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2022.e02197>.